

Influence of long-term crop management practices on grain yield and incidence of brown planthopper (BPH) in rice at Siruguppa, Karnataka, India.

Treatment no.	Treatment ^a N:P:K:Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)	BPH hill ⁻¹ (no.) (90 DAT)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹) (1999 kharif)	Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹) (1991-98 kharif)
T1	100:50:50:20	2.60 f	5.3 c	4.3
T2	150:75:75:20	3.57 ef	5.9 b	5.0
T3	200:100:100:20	6.93 c	6.2 ab	5.1
T4	T2 + FYM (5 t ha ⁻¹)	4.57 de	6.3 ab	5.1
T5	T2 + Gli. (3 t ha ⁻¹)	4.70 de	5.9 b	5.2
T6	T2 + Ses. (5 t ha ⁻¹)	4.83 de	5.9 b	5.1
T7	T2 + FYM (5 t ha ⁻¹) + Gli. (3 t ha ⁻¹) + Ses. (5 t ha ⁻¹)	5.57 cd	6.0 ab	5.2
T8	T2 + 25% more PP	4.63 de	6.4 ab	4.9
T9	T3 + FYM (5 t ha ⁻¹) + Gli. (3 t ha ⁻¹) + Ses. (5 t ha ⁻¹)	9.00 b	6.3 ab	5.3
T10	T9 + 25% more PP	11.27 a	6.5 a	5.2

^aNumbers in a column followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% by Duncan's multiple range test. Gli. = *Gliricidia*, Ses. = *Sesbania*, DAT = days after transplanting, PP = plant population.

during the 1999 kharif season. The mean yield over the 1991-98 kharif seasons also indicated a similar trend. Results suggest that applying medium fertilizer doses (150:75:75:20) with organic manures, combined with a normal plant population, gave better yields than using a higher dose of organic and inorganic nutrient sources coupled with a higher plant population, without encouraging BPH incidence.

Effect of intercropping grain legume and green manure for multiple use on rice

R. Kalpana, S.P. Palaniappan, and S. Mythili, Department of Agronomy, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU), Coimbatore, India

Multipurpose legumes can be grown in the summer, grain and haulms harvested (for fodder), and the ratooned regrowth used as green manure for the following rice crop. By adopting such a system, farmers get additional income from legume grains, fodder for animals, and green manure for rice. One such system involving red gram and green gram intercropped with two green manure crops was evaluated.

Field experiments were conducted at TNAU, Coimbatore, during the summer (Mar-Jun) and monsoon (Jul-Oct) seasons. The soil of the experimental field was black clay, classified taxonomically as Vertic Ustochreft, with low available N, medium available P, and high available K. Pre-ribe crops included grain legumes, such as green gram (*Vigna radiata*) variety

CO 45 and red gram (*Cajanus cajan*) variety ICPH 73, and green manure crops *Sesbania rostrata* and *S. aculeata*. In the intercropped stand, grain legumes and green manure crops were raised in a 3:1 proportion. The grain legume and green manure treatments were laid out in a randomized block design and replicated thrice.

The green manure crops were cut 45 d after sowing at a height of 30 cm from the ground using sickles. Immediately after cutting, plants were irrigated and allowed to regenerate. Green gram was harvested and the haulms were removed for fodder. Red gram was harvested by picking the pods; the remaining red gram stalks and green manure biomass were cut and incorporated *in situ*. These were allowed to decompose for 10 d and then

the succeeding rice crop was transplanted. Variety CO 45 was raised in a split-plot design and replicated thrice with eight treatment combinations of grain legumes and green manure crops in the main plots and three levels of N (0, 50, and 100 kg ha⁻¹) in the subplots. Biometric observations and yield were recorded at different stages of crop growth for pre-ribe crops and rice.

Results indicated that *S. rostrata* yielded significantly higher biomass than *S. aculeata* and hence contributed significantly more to rice. The intercrop treatments resulted in significantly higher biomass and N accumulation over the sole grain treatments. Grain legumes yielded 0.3–0.4 t ha⁻¹ when intercropped with green manure crops. The green manure crops

gave 10.3–13.4 t of fodder ha⁻¹ and their ratoon regrowth contributed 4.7–7.5 t of green manure biomass ha⁻¹. Incorporation of red gram stalks and ratooned green manure biomass contributed 16–55 kg N ha⁻¹ (Table 1).

Rice yield, obtained by incorporating sole *S. rostrata*/*S. aculeata* along with the application of 50 kg N ha⁻¹, was on a par with yield from the treatment with 100 kg N ha⁻¹, resulting in a savings of 50 kg N ha⁻¹. It was also found that after applying sole *Sesbania* spp. without fertilizer N, rice yields (3.6 t ha⁻¹) were on a par with yields obtained with 50 kg N ha⁻¹ alone (3.8 t ha⁻¹). These results show the possibility of saving 50 kg N ha⁻¹ by incorporating green manure (Table 2).

Table 1. Biomass production and yield of grain legumes and green manure crops.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biomass removed for fodder (t ha ⁻¹)	Biomass incorporated (t ha ⁻¹)	N contribution (kg ha ⁻¹)
Sole GG	0.4	7.4	–	–
Sole RG	0.7	6.8	3.1	16.7
Sole SA	–	22.7	12.0	73.5
Sole SR	–	24.9	15.6	82.2
GG + SA	0.3	12.2	4.8	33.5
GG + SR	0.3	13.4	5.5	42.5
RG + SA	0.4	10.3	70.4	50.9
RG + SR	0.3	11.2	7.5	55.8
CD (P = 0.05)	–	1.32	0.11	0.70

^aGG = green gram, RG = red gram, SA = *Sesbania aculeata*, SR = *S. rostrata*.

Table 2. Grain yield of rice (t ha⁻¹).

Treatment ^a	N ₀	N ₅₀	N ₁₀₀	Mean
Sole GG	2.7	3.8	4.6	3.7
Sole RG	3.0	4.3	5.0	4.1
Sole SA	3.6	5.6	6.0	5.0
Sole SR	3.6	5.6	6.1	5.1
GG + SA	3.2	4.8	5.2	4.4
GG + SR	3.3	4.8	5.3	4.5
RG + SA	3.4	5.0	5.4	4.6
RG + SR	3.5	5.1	5.7	4.8
Mean	3.3	4.9	5.4	
		SEd	CD (P = 0.05)	
T		0.17	0.36	
N		0.10	0.21	
T at N		0.29	0.61	
N at T		0.30	0.61	

^aGG = green gram, RG = red gram, SA = *Sesbania aculeata*, SR = *S. rostrata*, SEd = Standard error of the difference.

Comparative growth performance of rice and the weed *Echinochloa oryzicola* in lowland and upland conditions

N. Trillana, IRRI; R. Chaudhary, Participatory Rural Development Foundation, India; T. Inamura and T. Horie, Faculty of Agriculture, Kyoto University, Japan E-mail: n.trillana@cgiar.org

Most upland rice cultivars grow successfully in flooded conditions, whereas most lowland rice cultivars can survive in well-watered aerobic soils. It is known that rice has C₃ photosynthesis, whereas the weed *Echinochloa oryzicola* possesses a C₄ photosynthetic pathway. It was hypothesized that plant species with a C₄ photosynthetic pathway had a greater growth rate than C₃ plants (Black 1971). Scientists such as Baskin and Baskin (1978) reviewed several studies and obtained results that generally disagreed with the hypothesis. They

suggested that many factors other than the C₄ pathway are more important in determining plant growth rate. Little is known about the comparative growth performance of rice in upland and lowland field conditions with *E. oryzicola* as a “vegetative mimic” of rice. This study compared the growth performance of rice and *E. oryzicola* under upland and lowland conditions and determined related photosynthetic traits such as stomatal conductance and net photosynthetic rate.

A field experiment was conducted at the Kyoto University

crop science experimental site. Two rice cultivars of different ecotypes—IET1444, an indica upland rice that originated from India, and Nipponbare, a lowland japonica from Japan—and the weed *E. oryzicola* were used in this study. Upland and lowland fields were prepared and laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Fourteen-day-old seedlings were transplanted in the field. In the upland field, watering was done three times a week; in the lowland field, continuous irrigation was employed by maintaining a 2–3-